

Project number: 874662
Project Acronym: HEAP

Project Title: Human Exposome Assessment Platform

Project Website URL: <https://heap-exposome.eu/>

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Project Deliverable

D1.2: Sustainability Plan

Deliverable due date: 2025-06-30

Deliverable due month: M66

Document history

Version	Date	Changes	By	Reviewed
1.0	2025-06-16	First draft	Roxana Merino	Joakim Dillner
1.0	2025-06-28	Specific contributions from the partners	Evert-Ben van Veen Heimo Müller Ville Pimenoff Juha Törnroos Frederik Trier Møller Heather Coombs Marek Nowicki Zisis Kozlakidis	Roxana Merio Helena Andersson

Executive Summary

This deliverable outlines the HEAP plan to ensure that the project's results continue contributing to exposome research beyond the project's lifetime. To better understand how HEAP can continue contributing to other projects and initiatives related to exposome research or biomedical research, the HEAP sustainable components are grouped into web services, IT infrastructure, software platform, analysis pipelines, wearable devices, and data.

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Introduction

The HEAP project involves innovation in ICT and exposome research. The project has notable achievements in both areas, which are expected to continue contributing to exposome research beyond the project's lifetime.

In the ICT area, HEAP provides a PaaS based on Hopsworks (<https://www.hopsworks.ai/>) that enables the distributed storage and analysis of heterogeneous datasets. It also offers state-of-the-art tools and frameworks for developing bioinformatics pipelines and machine learning (ML)/deep learning (DL) models for knowledge discovery from data. The integration with R-Studio enables the use and development of R pipelines and their integration with other bioinformatics and machine learning workflows.

The HEAP platform is deployed on the CSC Infrastructure for Research. CSC is a long-term, well-established research infrastructure funded by the Finnish government that provides state-of-the-art ICT resources and services.

Other relevant HEAP results include the reuse and improvement of BIBBOX, an integrated research software framework for sample and research data management and pre-processing, and the HEAP catalogue, which is now part of the Molgenis EHEN catalogue.

HEAP includes six different exposome cohorts, which provide samples, data, analysis tools, and relevant results published in scientific journals.

HEAP has created a governance guideline for conducting research through the HEAP technical platform based on the most common use cases for research via the platform. The guidelines ensure that research institutions, whether former HEAP partners or others, have the ethical guidance and legal tools available for such research.

This sustainability plan aims to maintain the usability of HEAP achievements, including data, software tools, Platform as a Service (PaaS), infrastructure, and scientific results.

The HEAP Sustainability Levels

Sustainability of the web services

HEAP Website

After the project's completion, the HEAP website (<https://heap-exposome.eu/>) will be transferred from IARC to KI (the Coordinator) and maintained by the KI partner for five years (until June 2030).

HEAP metadata catalogue

HEAP utilised MOLGENIS EMX2 as the software platform for the metadata catalogue, which is identical to the proposed EHEN catalogue. Partner MUG is hosting the HEAP catalogue. The HEAP catalogue data was mirrored (harvested) into the EHEN catalogue. If it is necessary to replicate the HEAP EHEN's data, KI will host the HEAP catalogue for the required time.

HEAP Toolbox

MUG hosted the FAIR toolbox throughout the project. Following the project's completion, MUG will continue to host the demo and test environment and maintain the source code on GitHub (<https://github.com/bibbox/sys-bibbox>). BBMRI-ERIC will host a dedicated landing page (<https://bibbox.bbmri-eric.eu/>) and comprehensive documentation for the HEAP/BIBBOX Toolbox, ensuring the long-term sustainability and accessibility of the developed solution.

HEAP FAIR Self-Assessment Tool

The FAIR assessment tool enables users to evaluate the levels of FAIRness in their datasets. It is a web service maintained and hosted by MUG. The survey, used for both self-assessment and final assessment of the "FAIRness" of the hEAP cohorts, will be available after the project end at <https://heap.bibbox.org/surveys/?s=XC8YLX8W8R>. With this tool, users can evaluate the FAIRness of datasets in terms of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability.

The DUC/CCE tools, <https://duc.le.ac.uk>, were used to evaluate machine-readable licence descriptions and data use conditions. These tools remain available beyond the end of the HEAP project. The University of Leicester will continue to maintain them, with ongoing involvement from a member of the HEAP consortium.

Sustainability of the infrastructure (IaaS)

CSC has provided the infrastructure (IaaS) used in the project, IT Centre for Science Ltd. CSC has developed the HEAP Information Commons (IC), described in D10.1, which enables the utilisation of data management and computation resources in the project.

CSC is a non-profit enterprise owned by the Finnish state. According to a documented free-of-charge use policy (<https://research.csc.fi/free-of-charge-use>), CSC provides services for Finnish research free of charge. In principle, CSC's services are available free of charge for Finnish researchers and research projects with a principal investigator affiliated with a Finnish university or higher education institute. Services might also be available for research purposes for other users.

Therefore, the infrastructure developed and used in the project is available free of charge to Finnish researchers and others, provided on a case-by-case basis by the service coordinator at the Karolinska Institute.

Sustainability of the platform (PaaS)

The HEAP platform is an open-source customised solution that integrates Hopsworks and CSC according to HEAP requirements. Hopsworks and CSC develop and implement the integration. Regarding sustainability, the HEAP platform will continue its development beyond the project's lifetime through the Hopsworks developer team and community. Exposome and other biomedical research projects or institutions can approach KI as an intermediary to deploy the HEAP platform on a case-by-case basis.

The HEAP coordination team is participating in the RI EIRENE, Swedish node proposal. HEAP coordination team presented HEAP at the EIRENE Swedish event on April 18th, 2023 (<https://www.scilifelab.se/event/eirene-sweden-symposium-on-the-exposome/>), and is taking part in the EIRENE PPP for the Swedish node. The aim is to reuse HEAP PaaS, software tools and UPAS devices as services offered by the research infrastructure for exposome and metabolome research. The HEAP participant UOULU is part of IHEN/EIRENE and continues to reuse UPAS devices in the newly accredited project to monitor the offspring of previously pregnant women.

Sustainability of the software analysis tools

HEAP's used and produced software is open source. HEAP maintains a GitHub repository (<https://github.com/HEAP-EXPOSOME>) for the tools and pipelines available to the research community. Open source enables software sustainability by allowing developer communities to continue developing, updating, and improving the software.

The open-source analysis tools developed by the partners are registered in the Elixir bio.tools as a direct contribution to IHEN, with the respective links to GitHub:

Tool	Description	Link Bio.tools	GitHub
HEAP-Hopworks	Data-Intensive AI platform with a Feature Store. Open-source PaaS for distributed data management, data analysis, and machine learning based on Hopworks: https://www.hopworks.ai/ https://docs.hopworks.ai/latest/ Deployed at CSC – IT Center for Science: https://heap-hopworks.csc.fi/login	https://bio.tools/heap-hopworks	https://github.com/HEAP-EXPOSOME/hopworks
My Purchases Pipeline/enrich_cpd	Custom-made pipeline for matching and validating specific products, i.e., a specific brand of whole milk, to generic products, "full milk", and enriching the generic product with information from food databases.	https://bio.tools/enrich_cpd	https://github.com/HEAP-EXPOSOME/ConsumerData
Methylation Preprocessing	R package for preprocessing and initial QC of Illumina DNA methylation microarray data. (450K, EPIC v1.0, EPIC v2.0) Two-step preprocessing of raw array data (.idat files): (1) for each methylation bead chip (containing several arrays/samples), (2) combines information from individual bead chips	https://bio.tools/methylation_preprocessing	https://github.com/HEAP-EXPOSOME/eut_opsQC

Epigenetic age prediction	R package for estimating epigenetic age from Illumina DNA methylation microarray data. THE WID_clocks function uses a methylation beta matrix and returns the WID general, epithelial and immune clocks. It also returns the WID-relative-epithelial-age (WID_rea) and WID-relative-immune-age (WID_ria) (Δ WID epithelial or WID immune and WID general clock). https://genomebiology.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13059-022-02603-3	https://bio.tools/epigenetic_age_prediction	https://github.com/HEAP-EXPOSOME/WIDclocks
HPV-KITE	A Java application to be run on a laptop, cluster, or supercomputer to cross-check the sequences with the HPV viruses from the database.	https://bio.tools/hpv-kite	https://github.com/HEAP-EXPOSOME/HPV-KITE
HPV-Meta	A pipeline to detect human papillomavirus (HPV) transcripts in RNA sequencing (RNA-seq) data. Designed to enhance the accuracy of HPV detection and minimise false positives due to contamination, HPV-meta is particularly valuable in cancer genomics research. Ure A, Mukhedkar D, Arroyo Mühr LS. Using HPV-meta for human papillomavirus RNA quality detection. Scientific Reports. 2022 Jul 29;12(1):13058. doi:10.1038/s41598-022-17318-5.	https://bio.tools/hpv-meta	https://github.com/HEAP-EXPOSOME/HPV-meta
KITE	A Java application aiming to detect any combination of microbe genomes selected to be detected from metagenome data.	https://bio.tools/kite	https://github.com/HEAP-EXPOSOME/KITE
Biopipe	A pipeline for taxonomic classification of microbiome profiles and subsequent diversity analysis is suitable for both WGS and RNA-Seq. Bash and R scripts.	https://bio.tools/biopipe	https://github.com/HEAP-EXPOSOME/biopipe

Biotic	Pipeline for comprehensive environmental taxonomic classification application, including control of false-positive taxa detection.	https://bio.tools/biotic	https://github.com/PimenoffV/biotic
Metagenome assembly	Pipeline for parallel computing of improved metagenomic assembly using Spark-based computing and Hopsworks platform	https://bio.tools/metagenome_assembly	https://github.com/HEAP-EXPOSOME/megahit-assembly
VIBE-UPAS	Visualisation of Integrated Biological Exposures from UPAS wearable devices. Shiny app for visualizing the personalized exposome.	https://bio.tools/vibe-upas	https://github.com/PimenoffV/VIBE
Abiotic	Pipeline for chemical exposome integration and analysis with biotic data	https://bio.tools/abiotic	https://github.com/PimenoffV/Abiotic

Sustainability of the data

All the cohort's data is, in principle, sensitive. Once the project ends, the partners (the data controllers) should store and maintain the non-Finnish data. Whether the data resides on the institution's premises or in an EU infrastructure, such as EUDAT, EGA or EOSC, the data should remain FAIR. For instance, epigenetic data from UIBK will be stored in the Elixir-provided European Genome Archive (EGA) and made available upon request, using harmonised Data Access Agreements and with appropriate oversight from the Data Access Committee. The cohorts' metadata is FAIR and available through the EHEN catalogue.

EHEN will maintain the EHEN metadata catalogue, which each cohort's designated responsible person will update. It will ensure that information and metadata remain available to stimulate collaboration and reuse of HEAP data and knowledge.

HEAP provides legacy non-sensitive data to learn and test the platform. This is the case for environmental wastewater data from 19 Swedish sites, collected before, during, and after the COVID-19 pandemic. The data consists of sequencing and mass spectrometry analysis results, which were tested using bioinformatics pipelines and machine learning (ML) models during BYOD #5. Other legacy data include one anonymised dataset from the Swedish cervical cancer screening program and synthetic data produced from the Finnish HPV vaccination cohort.

Maternity cohort and wearable monitoring data, as demonstrated during the BYOD session, focused on scientific publications in progress.

On the other hand, the Cohort marker papers are a starting point for data reusability and future collaborations:

Sustainability of the My Purchases cohort

The My Purchases cohort will continue to collect data, funded by a recent donation, for at least three years after the HEAP project ends. Furthermore, a full version of the data collected from 650 volunteers will be available for future research through the Danish National Archives <https://en.rigsarkivet.dk/>.

Finally, the knowledge gained from the HEAP project has led to a continuation project, where consumer data will be used for real-life outbreak investigation work. The data collection from the My Purchases cohort is sustained.

<https://sundhedsdonationer.dk/projekter/forbrugerdata-skal-forbedre-opklaring-af-foedevarebaaren-sygdom/>

Sustainability of the Exposometers

The clinical study “Monitoring exposures during pregnancy with a wearable device” included 100 pregnant women from the Finnish cohort who wore UPAS (Ultrasonic Personal Air Sampler) to monitor exposures during the 3 months of pregnancy (D5.4). One hundred units were acquired during the study, and KI acquired 10 additional units (updated version) for monitoring the work environment and generating data for BYOD #5. This dataset is part of the HEAP legacy data and serves as proof of concept for the UOAS use. The exposometer was presented and tested by participants in BYOD #5. Work environment data produced at Karolinska Institutet from three different sites was presented in the workshop, and is openly available through the HEAP common data repository.

KI has disseminated the UPAS in the proposal for EIRENE Sweden and a national project proposal at Karolinska Institutet. UOULU has acquired ethical approval and funding for a new project to monitor the offspring of recently pregnant women. UOULU has also submitted UPAS-based applications for more clinically oriented exposome studies within the EU HORIZON framework.

Impact beyond HEAP

A central idea of the proposal was to disseminate the HEAP results globally, enabling their use beyond the consortium and the EU.

IARC is a crucial partner in ensuring the sustainability of HEAP outputs by advancing exposome research related to cancer. The HEAP symposium “From Information to Action,” organised by IARC in May 2024, was a concrete step towards this aim and featured several presentations from members of IARC’s global network.

Following this, other strategic educational and outreach activities for a scientific audience include the HEAP webinar series in 2025, which enabled contacts in the IARC network (BCNet, IARC Learning) to receive guidance on good governance and data management of exposome research projects, the responsible use of wearable technology in observational research, and a HEAP use case demonstration (planned for Autumn 2025).

A one-day meeting with a group of first-year students in dietetics and Nutrition from the University of Wageningen (February 2025) was part of the IARC strategy to promote the concept of the exposome and exposomics, with the HEAP platform presented as a potential research tool for international collaboration in cancer research.

A visit from high school students to IARC, to tour the biobank and labs, provided an opportunity to pilot learning activities for the general public on biobanking and broad consent, highlighting the importance of public participation and support for science and research.

HEAP outreach projects have targeted the general public to explain the exposome concept and give examples of exposome research projects via a 5-minute online survey, [“Your Exposome”](#).

All these learning and outreach activities were recorded and are available in the HEAP and EHEN online toolboxes.

Some concrete steps towards the reuse and sustainability of HEAP are:

- EIRENE-Sweden
- CSC long-term hosting - KI broker
- IARC worldwide dissemination, training and education in collaboration with the HEAP partners, especially Hopsworks, pipeline providers, and use cases
- Cohort marker papers
- EU and national grants

Future Plans

1. KI is part of the Preparatory Phase of EIRENE Sweden, proposing HEAP as a standard research software platform.

2. The HEAP Coordination team is negotiating a long-term hosting arrangement for the HEAP Hopsworks instance at CSC, with KI as the proxy to manage its use.
3. EU and national proposals, including the HEAP platform, wearable devices, and published results, are ongoing.
4. IARC will promote the HEAP platform as a tool for exposomics data analysis to its LMIC network (the primary channel being BCNet [<https://bcnet.iarc.fr/>]) through the final webinar in the HEAP webinar series, where a HEAP use case utilising the informatics platform will be demonstrated. The recording of the use case will be available via the HEAP and EHEN toolboxes.
5. Through BCNet, IARC has already identified Egypt (an IARC participating state) as a potential pilot for the future HEAP informatics platform in LMIC countries. A BCNet representative from Egypt (Head of Community, Environmental and Occupational Medicine, School of Medicine, Ain Shams University) attended and presented at the HEAP Symposium in 2024, and has presented on HEAP and exposomics within Egypt (Annual conference of Egyptian Toxicology Society 2025). She would serve as a key contact for future projects.
6. HEAP tools and outputs are recorded and stored in an easily accessible format via the online toolboxes on the HEAP website (heap-exposome.eu) and the European Human Exposome Network (EHEN) website (humanexposome.eu). KI will host and maintain both websites until June 2030.
7. Through its participation in the International Human Exposome Network (IHEN), IARC will promote HEAP tools and outputs to the global community. HEAP tools for researchers and bioinformaticians will also feature in the IHEN toolbox on the IHEN website (humanexposome.net).
8. At the time of writing (June 2025), IARC is participating in discussions between the scientific networks and research infrastructures IHEN, NEXUS (USA) and EIRENE, to formalise a super-network devoted to exposomics (current working title: the Global Exposome Forum). Promotion of the outputs of HEAP will be among the aims of such a network.
9. The knowledge gained from the HEAP WP4 project has led to a continuation project in Denmark, where consumer data will be used for real-life outbreak investigation work. Thus, the project will move from research to direct use for public health, using a method that, if successful, may be applicable in many EU countries.
<https://sundhedsdonationer.dk/projekter/forbrugerdata-skal-forbedre-opklaring-af-foedevarebaaren-sygdom/>

